

Preliminary Considerations on BANTER: A European Project on Innovative Ammonia Bimodal Nuclear Rocket

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Since the 1950s, nuclear reactors have been proposed for space use in both thermonuclear and nuclear-electric propulsion systems. In more recent years, bimodal nuclear propulsion systems have also been proposed. In this case, bimodality refers to the fact that two propulsion systems (the thermonuclear and the electric one) share an element, namely the nuclear reactor. However, the two propulsion systems do not share the same propellant (generally, hydrogen and xenon, respectively). A great advantage of nuclear bimodal systems is that they can generate electrical power anywhere in the solar system, not depending on the distance from the sun like traditional solar electric propulsion. Moreover, the inclusion of a Brayton cycle that uses the reactor as a hot source is the best solution in terms of cycle efficiency/mass ratio. Other types of propulsion systems, in which the same propellant is used for both chemical propulsion and electric propulsion, have been proposed in the literature and have demonstrated that they provide lower masses and dimensions than systems using only one of the two propulsion solutions, as well as guaranteeing a broadening of the spectrum of missions achievable thanks to the versatility in the type of maneuvers that can be carried out. In this context, the University of Pisa will lead during the next four years an European Commission funded project called BANTER. The BANTER project proposes the first bimodal nuclear propulsion system in which the same propellant is used for both thermonuclear and electric propulsion. The selected propellant is ammonia (NH₃). Hydrogen has long been favored as the primary propellant for nuclear thermal propulsion systems, dating back to the 60's Rover/NERVA program; its low molecular weight provides exceptional specific impulse outclassing traditional chemical propulsion systems. However, hydrogen's low density, cryogenic storage requirements, and absence as a direct resource on potential space mission destinations complicate its use. Moreover, the use of hydrogen for interplanetary or multiple-round trip missions increases the propulsion system development cost and time due to the excessive complexity required by the propellant management subsystem. NH₃, with its high hydrogen content and potential for non-cryogenic storage, offers a viable alternative, especially with the discovery of NH₃ resources on the Moon and Mars. NH₃ simplifies system design but comes with the drawback of reduced specific impulse, halving its performance compared to hydrogen due to the highest molecular weight. The proposed radically new technology will contribute to bridge this performance gap. In the BANTER project, NH₃ has a triple function: i) propellant for the thermonuclear component; ii) propellant for the electric component; iii) working fluid for an open and asynchronous Brayton cycle generating the required electrical power. A fundamental principle of the innovative nuclear reactor design is to achieve the NH₃ decomposition into nitrogen and hydrogen within the reactor core before being accelerated in the nozzle. This reaction will halve the molecular weight of the exhaust gases and increase the specific impulse to approximately 500 s, thus exceeding the performance provided by chemical thrusters using cryogenic propellants, without having to bring complex and voluminous tanks into orbit, significantly reducing the overall system dimensions and launch costs. The classical power generation systems using the bimodal nuclear reactors in space have two main drawbacks: the fluid absorbs heat passing through the walls of the nozzle and the moderator eliminating the heat generated after firing the NTP, this greatly limits the generated amount of electrical power and the times in which it can be provided; the only way the system has to disperse waste heat is through radiation towards open space, this forces the inclusion of radiators with enormous masses and envelopes. BANTER tries to eliminate these drawbacks by using the NH₃ extracted by an E-pump from the main propellant tank as the working fluid for an open asynchronous Brayton cycle. In this cycle, the NH₃ passes through the nuclear reactor to change phase and absorb heat. Then, the gaseous NH₃ expands in a turbine, converting work into electric power thanks to a generator connected to the turbine shaft; this power feeds the electric thrusters and the E-pumps. The NH₃ exiting from the turbine flows towards a second NH₃ tank initially empty. Different solutions are implemented to keep the pressure inside this tank below the threshold imposed by the turbine operating conditions. The tank is connected to a series of warm gas thrusters that vent the excess of vapor NH₃ by generating small thrust for the spacecraft attitude control; a flow of liquid NH₃ can be directed using an E-pump from the main tank to a mixer at the entrance of the second tank where it reduces the vapor NH₃ temperature and enhance its condensation; the excess of vapor NH₃ can be sent towards the main tank to perform autogenous pressurization of the propellant NH₃ and maintain a constant feeding pressure for the E-pumps (reduction of cavitation phenomena probability).

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